

AUTOMOTIVE TOOLSET AND SERVICE IMPLEMENTATION

Deliverable D4.2

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Deliverable

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Executive Summary

The objective of TARGET-X project is to accelerate the digitalization of four verticals (i.e., energy, construction, automotive, and manufacturing) by deploying large-scale trials testbeds. Work package 4 focuses on the automotive vertical and how the 5G network will enhance the experience in such vertical. In this context, this deliverable describes the toolsets developed for the integration and validation of the three use cases of WP4 (Cooperative perception, digital twins, predictive quality of service for tele-operated driving), in addition to some preliminary results about network performance using Qualcomm measurement and logging devices.

This document describes in detail the connectivity architecture used in this project, both for the mobile network and the Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) infrastructure and will address it from the functional and physical points of view. A detailed description of the tele-operated vehicle used in one of the use cases is also provided. Likewise, an extensive report is presented on the measurements carried out by Qualcomm on the IDIADA mobile network, where the performance of this network has been evaluated in its entirety.

Finally, a detailed description of the use cases is provided together with their functional view, a description of the measured KPIs, and preliminary results obtained in the track tests.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
APN	Access Point Name
AS	Application Server
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BSC	Base Station Controller
BW	Bandwidth
CA	Carrier Aggregation
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CAV	Connected and Automated Vehicle
CC	Carriers
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System
CN	Core Network
CPM	Collective Perception Message
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything
CVH	Connected Vehicle Hub
CWS	Collision Warning Service
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DL	Down Link
DSRC	Dedicated Short-Range Communications
EN-DC	E-UTRAN NR Dual Connectivity
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FDD	Frequency Duplex Division
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HO	Handover
IDL	Interface Definition Language
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
IVS	In-Vehicle System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDMS	Local Dynamic Map Service
LTE	Long Term Evolution

MCS	Manoeuvre Coordination Service
MEC	Mobile Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple In Multiple Out
MOCN	Multi-Operator Core Network
NR	New Radio
OAM	Operations, Administration, and Maintenance
OBU	On Board Unit
PF	Prediction Function
QoS	Quality of Service
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RNC	Radio Network Controller
RSU	Road Side Units
RTK	Real Time Kinematic
TDD	Time Division Duplex
ToC	Tele-operation Centre
ToD	Tele-Operated Driving
ToV	Teleoperated Vehicle
TRX	Transceiver
UE	User Equipment
UL	Up Link
UMTS	Universal Mobile Telecommunications System
V2I-DSS	Vehicle – Infrastructure Data Sharing Service
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
VM	Virtual Machine

1 Introduction

The automotive vertical of the TARGET-X project focuses on use cases that enhance road safety, and transportation quality of experience, cost, and duration. In particular, this WP focuses on developing and testing various use cases using IDIADA's infrastructure, including mobile networks, Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) platform, and testing tracks. Furthermore, network infrastructure has been improved with the deployment of a Mobile Edge Computing (MEC), and mobile network performance will be tested using different tools.

Within the automotive vertical, task T4.2 focuses on the development of a toolset for the deployment and evaluation of the automotive use cases. The following activities are expected to be executed along this task:

- C-ITS platform and services deployment
- Virtual Machines (VMs) configuration
- Digital Twin service development
- Tele-operated Vehicle (ToV) infrastructure and service deployment
- Predictive Quality of Service (QoS) concept, architecture, and deployment
- HMI development
- Service Key Performance Indicator (KPI) measurement tool development and deployment
- Mobile network performance testing, data collection, and analysis

This deliverable describes in detail IDIADA connectivity architecture, the connected vehicles, the ToV, and how they are used by the different use cases with a detailed description of the three use cases: Cooperative perception, digital twins, predictive Quality of Service (QoS) for Tele-operated Driving (ToD). Furthermore, the deliverable will provide preliminary results based on a testing campaign held on September 2024.

1.1 Document structure

The document is structured as follows: In section 2, we will describe the IDIADA connectivity architecture including its cellular network physical and functional view in addition to the C-ITS network physical, functional, and communication view. In section 3, we will provide a description of the ToV infrastructure, services, and testing setup. In section 4, we will describe the advanced Services: Collision Warning Service (CWS) and predictive QoS for ToD. In section 5, we will present a summary of the performance measurements performed by Qualcomm over the 5G network. In section 6, the uses cases will be presented. Finally, the deliverable will present the conclusions in Section 7.

2 IDIADA connectivity architecture

This section will explain in depth all mobile infrastructure currently deployed at IDIADA, including the cellular network and the Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) platform. We will see in detail all the views involved to have a clear understanding of the possibilities that this infrastructure can provide for a successful deployment of TARGET-X use cases.

2.1 Cellular Network

Cooperative systems testing is more complex than traditional automotive testing because these systems interact with various Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) components, including vehicles, pedestrians, and road infrastructure. Today, most vehicles connect to external application servers, networks, and the Internet via embedded communication modules, drivers' smartphones, or integrated systems that host applications directly in the car's infotainment system.

With the emergence of new standards like C-V2X, beginning with 3GPP Release 14 that enhances LTE systems to support direct Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) communication, cellular networks are becoming crucial for deploying C-ITS technologies and advancing automation. In addition, 802.11p has already proven to be a reliable standard tailored to meet the requirements of V2X applications.

The gradual integration of these wireless technologies into vehicles will introduce a range of new cooperative and connected services, paving the way for fully autonomous vehicles. However, developing these services necessitates extensive and costly testing, highlighting the need for new testing tools and suites that ensure safety during evaluations.

While traditional test tracks are sufficient for standard vehicles, cooperative, connected, and automated vehicles demand new testing environments that can create a fully configurable and controlled networks, encompassing both physical and digital infrastructures to safely replicate test scenarios. Achieving specific challenging conditions often requires extensive travel, which can be resource-intensive, and in some regions, regulations prohibit certain tests on public roads. Additionally, commercial cellular networks lack the controlled conditions necessary for this type of testing, as their performance can vary based on user demand and operational factors.

To ensure reliable test results, it's essential to control network parameters and recreate specific scenarios. Moreover, commercial networks may not easily adopt the latest features needed for efficient and secure applications, as their implementation depends on the interests of mobile network operators. Keeping sensitive data within a private network can also help address privacy concerns.

IDIADA offers a private network solution that encompasses a comprehensive 2G/3G/4G/5G network at its central facilities in Santa Oliva, Tarragona, all adhering to 3GPP standards. Due to regulatory restrictions, the radio frequency spectrum is reserved for telecommunications operators, leading to a MOCN configuration, aligning IDIADA's private network with Orange's commercial network.

The technical solution is developed by Orange and Ericsson, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: IDIADA's private network solution general outline.

The solution implemented at IDIADA's facilities features its own Core Network (CN) for 2G, 4G, and 5G, along with a shared CN for 3G. This network is dedicated solely to data transmission and does not support voice services.

The transport network connects base stations to the Base BSC, RNC and EPC using IP over fibre optic links, which ensures high reliability, fast performance, and low latency. External application servers can connect directly to the internal network or via broadband, depending on the testing requirements.

Radio access network links UE through the air interface by employing various radio technologies. IDIADA's network comprises four base stations that support 2G, 3G, 4G, and 5G-NSA radio access technologies, all configured with the latest software and network features. The collaboration with Orange Spain allows IDIADA to use all common frequency bands, enabling the creation of specific network scenarios with adjustable coverage across these technologies and frequency bands. This partnership permits the use of commercial frequency bands for all access technologies.

Further details about the Radio Access Network (RAN) components can be seen in Figure 2.

RAN configuration per site 2G + 3G + LTE + 5G TDD

Figure 2: RAN Configuration.

IDIADA's private network radio solution is based on the same hardware and software elements as commercial networks. There are no specific nodes, Hardware Activation Codes (HWAC), or software tailored for a private network solution.

The network's bands and capacities are as follows:

- 2G: 1 TRX per sector. Band 1800 MHz (B3)
- 3G: 1 UMTS Carrier. Band 900 MHz (B8). Bandwidth (BW) 5MHz
- 4G: 1 LTE Carrier. Band 1800 MHz (B3). BW 20 MHz
1 LTE Carrier. Band 2100 MHz (B1). BW 10 MHz
- 5G: 1 NR Carrier. Band 3500 MHz (N78). BW 60 MHz

The network is distributed across 4 nodes strategically positioned to cover the entire installation with maximum performance capabilities. Figure 3 illustrates the location of the 4 nodes with their 9 sectors and the coverage distribution they provide.

Figure 3: Cellular network coverage map.

IDIADA has its own SIM cards divided into different Access Point Names (APNs). Each APN is configured with specific routing conditions so that the APNs used internally by IDIADA can connect

to IDIADA's own servers, while those used by clients do not have this capability. Each APN allows all SIM cards within it to have visibility among themselves but not to see other APNs. This setup enables multiple clients on tracks to have direct visibility between their devices without interfering in tests with other clients. Additionally, all APNs have SIM cards with different QoS to conduct tests under different conditions.

The services offered over the network are varied and aim at enabling clients to test under degraded network conditions:

- Handovers between different technologies.
- Emulation of low coverage areas by reducing power in the nodes.
- Disabling Carrier Aggregation (CA) and Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) for testing under adverse network performance conditions.
- Adding fixed latencies to services.
- Stressing the network by reducing bandwidth in 4G and 5G.

5G SA technology is in the design phase for a middle term deployment, with which we will be able to exploit all the features and virtues associated with 5G, such as latencies between 1 and 4 ms or DL throughputs up to 20 Gbps and UL up to 230 Mbps [1].

The services offered with the IDIADA cellular network include the possibility of configuring 4G+5G Carrier Aggregation (CA) using only the two 4G carriers or disabling it completely to only have traffic with a single carrier. In addition, the MIMO configuration can be modified from the standard 4x4 to a 4x2 or 2x2 configuration. Modifying network characteristics enables a testing user to evaluate the performance of its systems in non-optimal situations. In parallel, power reductions can be applied to all radio technologies (together or separately) to emulate adverse coverage level conditions.

If a testing user wants to evaluate the performance of its systems and services when moving from one technology to another, HO can be forced between the different RATs, so that it can move, for example, from being in a cell with 5G coverage to another with 2G. In this way, the user has the possibility to test mobility by making HO between cells of different technologies.

IDIADA network can be adapted to recreate different scenarios in which users can test their systems and services in a private and confidential environment, emulating features and issues of a public network.

2.1.1 Physical View

The server room is in the Electronics department. It divides both networks, IDIADA Network and Ericsson CORE Network. Both are interconnected to provide services to IDIADA's testing user and to allow running services and testing with interdependency among them. Figure 4 shows the physical view deployment.

Figure 4: Physical view deployment.

An Edge server was deployed by TARGET-X WP4 team to run latency critical services over the cellular network. This Edge server has direct connection to the IDIADA network, internet connection, and is accessible from the 4G/5G network.

2.1.2 Functional View

The CORE solution deployed at IDIADA counts with an own BSC for 2G and a virtualized CORE solution for 4G/5G, physically installed at IDIADA's premises. Due to the complexity of the solution, the 3G CORE is shared with Orange Network. The Figure 5 shows the block diagram scheme about IDIADA's CORE solution.

Figure 5: Functional view of the IDIADA's Cellular Network.

2.2 Intelligent Transport System

C-ITS is an overarching concept that enables vehicles, infrastructure, and other road users to communicate with each other in real time, providing data that supports safety, traffic management, and mobility applications. C-ITS messages are defined by various standards, including those developed by ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) and ISO.

IDIADA has its own ITS consisting of a self-developed platform that can manage standardized C-ITS messages and a robust infrastructure used to spread the information.

The key message types for C-ITS are Cooperative Awareness Message (CAM), Decentralized Environmental Notification Message (DENM), and Collective Perception Messages (CPM), each serving different purposes in vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication systems as it will be explained below.

2.2.1 CAM messages

CAM messages are used to broadcast basic information about a vehicle's status, such as its position, speed, direction, and other relevant dynamic data, to nearby vehicles and infrastructure. This allows surrounding entities to be aware of the vehicle's presence and behaviour, which is crucial for safety and situational awareness.

- **Transmission Frequency:** CAMs are transmitted periodically, typically every 1 second, but this can vary depending on the application and environment (e.g., urban, highway). In the deployed use cases of TARGET-X, we will be using 100 ms period no matter if we are moving or if we are stopped.
- **Message Structure:**
 - **Header Information:** Contains the message type and ID, as well as the transmission interval and time of transmission.
 - **Vehicle Information:** Includes vehicle ID, position (latitude, longitude, altitude), speed, direction, and other relevant dynamic parameters such as acceleration.

- **Safety Information:** Contains information about the vehicle's health (e.g., emergency status) and environment (e.g., road surface conditions).
- **Message Elements:**
 - **Basic Vehicle Data:** Latitude, Longitude, Altitude, Velocity, Heading, etc.
 - **Additional Data:** Vehicle type, registration ID, emergency status, etc.
 - **Transmission Timing:** Time of validity, timestamp of the message.

2.2.2 DENM message

DENM messages are designed to notify surrounding vehicles and infrastructures about specific environmental hazards or traffic events, such as accidents, roadworks, hazardous weather conditions, or other significant events that may affect road safety.

- **Transmission Frequency:** Unlike CAM, DENM messages are event-triggered. They are transmitted when a specific hazardous event occurs and are intended for urgent notification. Hence, they are transmitted at a higher frequency than CAMs.
- **Message Structure:**
 - **Header Information:** The message type and event description (e.g., accident, traffic obstruction).
 - **Event Information:** Details about the event such as its nature, severity, location, and any mitigation measures in place.
 - **Event Originator Information:** Who or what triggered the event (e.g., a vehicle, infrastructure, or a specific system).
 - **Event Location and Impact:** GPS coordinates, area of impact, road lanes involved and affected traffic directions.

2.2.3 CPM message

CPM messages allow vehicles and infrastructures to share information about other road users detected in the vicinity, such as pedestrians, bicycles, or other vehicles, even if they are not directly in the line of sight. This helps vehicles to perceive their environment more effectively and react to hazards in time.

- **Transmission Frequency:** CPMs are transmitted periodically and contain aggregated information about surrounding objects or road users that may not be visible to the vehicle, helping improve overall situational awareness.
- **Message Structure:**
 - **Header Information:** Includes basic metadata such as message type, timestamp, and transmission interval.
 - **Object Information:** Includes detailed information on detected objects, such as position (GPS coordinates), object type (e.g., vehicle, pedestrian, bicycle), movement (speed, direction), and detection confidence level.
 - **Sensor Data:** Details on the sensor or system (e.g., camera, radar) used to detect the object.

2.2.4 Functional view

The IDIADA connectivity architecture comprises a specific set of functions that allow the communication between the vehicles/stations and the infrastructure via C-ITS messages. The core

of this architecture is the ITS platform that manages the C-ITS messages flow from/to the rest of the stations (vehicles/RSUs).

As shown in Figure 6, there are three main functions that define IDIADA's ITS platform: the MQTT broker, the ITS Message generator, and the ITS Message extractor.

Figure 6: Functional view of the ITS Platform.

The MQTT broker queues messages into specific queues/topics, where clients can publish new messages to and/or subscribe to new messages from those queues/topics. This broker automatically distributes the stored or live published messages to the subscribers, who are following a smart subscription approach that adds geographically encoded information to the topics.

Such geographical information, based on the Quadtree tree-based data structure [2], leverages the native behaviour of the broker, which is intrinsically highly efficient and low-latency, to reach users based on their current location. This setup avoids additional services in the platform addressed to users' localization monitoring purposes.

The ITS Message generator converts non-ITS-compliant information to ITS standard messages. It accepts a set of minimum information that is translated into the ETSI ITS format and units, which are then used to generate the corresponding ITS standard messages. This function is compatible with cellular-based and DSRC/C-V2X technologies, meaning that it generates the messages to reach the stations connected to the platform via cellular technology and to the C-V2C RSUs deployed in the area.

The platform is compatible with CAM [3], DENM [4], CPM [5], IVIM [6], SREM [7], SSEM, MAPEM, SPATEM [8], VAM [7] and MCM [8] messages.

All messages published to the MQTT broker, either from the ITS Message Manager or from the in-field stations (vehicles, RSUs), are received by the ITS Message extractor. The latter converts the ETSI ITS format into a JSON-based representation. This allows external entities to interpret the messages without any knowledge of the ITS standards, easing processing and analysis tasks.

2.2.5 Physical view

The management of the V2X messages is carried out by the ITS platform which, from a physical point of view, is deployed in an EDGE computer deployed alongside IDIADA's CVH core servers, represented in Figure 7, to minimize the latency and maximize the performance when using cellular (2G/3G/4G/5G) technologies.

Such ITS platform consists of a set of docker services/containers orchestrated using Kubernetes.

Figure 7: IDIADA test tracks map with RSUs locations and Edge Computer.

2.3 Communication View

Internally, the ITS platform’s services communicate with each other using the MQTT protocol. This protocol is also used to communicate external ITS stations with the ITS platform. Only C-ITS messages are exchanged using this protocol, preventing any other format or data type to travel along with ITS data, which could potentially affect the system in terms of performance.

However, to abstract other non-ITS clients from ITS knowledge, the ITS Message Generator and the ITS Message Extractor offer REST API in/out interfaces to push/retrieve data. In this case, the input/output format is JSON.

Any client wanting to disseminate an ITS message to the platform shall generate an IDIADA’s proprietary JSON, which is a representation of every C-ITS message with simpler structure and standard units (e.g. meters-per-second instead of centimetres-per-second for the speed).

For the way back, if a client is interested in receiving the messages published in the ITS platform (either for the vehicles/RSUs or from the vehicle/RSUs) a client can extract them by consulting the ITS Message Extractor. The output format is the same as for the ITS Message Generator plus some metadata indicating the source of the information, publication topic, and timestamp. The communication flow could be seen at Figure 8.

Figure 8: Communication view ITS Platform

2.4 Vehicles

The connected vehicles could manage the C-ITS messages through a C-V2X network (using an On-Board Unit – OBU) or using 5G networks through a deployed 5G modem inside the car. The inside vehicle infrastructure is shown in figure 9.

Figure 9: Vehicle Communication View

3 Tele-operated driving system

3.1 Teleoperated driving

Driverless taxi services or operation of working machines and robots are becoming more and more common thanks to advanced network technologies and new business and job models. In this context, tele-operated Driving (ToD) [10] is gaining momentum in the car industry as either a futuristic standalone service (e.g. truck tele-operation, tele-operated valet parking, etc.) or enabler for autonomous driving.

IDIADA offers a teleoperated vehicle solution that allows to exploit the CVH network, as well as showcase the capacities of the company on the vehicle side as well.

This platform consists of three main components: the ToD Operator app, the ToD Application Service, and the MQTT broker as is showed in Figure 10.

The ToD Operator app is understood as the remote driver control system, which receives the input from the steering wheel and pedals and sends it to the ToD Application Service (AS). This service transforms the driver actions into commands understood by the vehicle's control unit ToD app, which reach the vehicle side via the MQTT broker and the 5G network.

Figure 10: Functional view of the ToD Platform.

3.2 CAVRide

The CAVRide, in relation to this project, has the capability to recreate CPMs thanks to the installed perception elements, such as Lidars and Radars. Additionally, through a Drive Kit, it can be controlled and driven remotely. To facilitate this, there are three cameras installed to provide the remote driver with a 180° view. The connection is handled by a 5G/4G router that gives connectivity from the car to the Remote-Control Centre and vice versa.

3.2.1 High Level Architecture Design

Figure 11 shows in the left side of the picture the remote centre room, composed by the commands (steering wheel and pedals), the screen with the views of the camaras, a laptop to orchestrate the remote driving, and a 5G router to provide mobile connectivity between the CAV-Ride and the remote room.

In the right side of the picture, we can see the components of the car, the three cameras to allow a 180° view, the drive kit that allows you to actuate remotely over the car, a laptop to orchestrate the remote driving and a 5G router to have mobile connectivity with the control room.

Figure 11 High level design components of the CAVRide.

4 Advanced Services

Although the presented cellular network and ITS Network offer a good baseline to match current needs for V2X applications, additional elements are required to perform advanced connectivity services. Two main services are described in the following sections: Collision Warning Service (CWS) and Predictive QoS for ToD.

4.1 Collision Warning Service (CWS)

The CWS is a system developed by IDIADA and deployed in the EDGE to predict collisions of vehicles using the information collected through CAM and CPM messages.

For developing a CWS, it was necessary to use classification algorithms for the task of distinguishing between hazardous and safe traffic conditions. Several classification algorithms have been investigated, namely:

- K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN)
- Support Vector Machines (SVMs)
- Relevance Vector Machines (RVMs)
- Random Forest (RFs)
- Gaussian Process (GPs)
- Neural Networks (NNs)

As in [11], SVMs show the best classification performance, and consistently produce the highest true to false positive ratio across multiple scenarios, especially when using under sampled or oversampled datasets. Therefore, SVMs were selected to perform the CWS.

The CWS, deployed in the infrastructure, operates at a frequency of 100 Hz, and the key role is evaluating collision risk between all objects (from CAM and CPM messages) by predicting trajectories based on the objects' heading and speed.

Those trajectories are compared to each other to assess collision risks both in space and time. When both dimensions collide under certain thresholds, a collision risk alert is emitted. Figure 12 shows the flow diagram of the CWS.

Figure 12: Flow diagram of CWS.

4.2 Predictive Quality of Service for ToD

To work properly, ToD requirements in terms of network performance (especially downlink latency, and uplink throughput and jitter) must be satisfied. Otherwise, the communication with the Tele-operated Vehicle (ToV) can be lost and the safety mechanisms of the latter (e.g., stop at the safety lane) will be triggered abruptly. This might lead to sudden stop that will be uncomfortable for the people in the ToV. Furthermore, there could be a need to send a person or a tow truck to recuperate the ToV, which might be costly, time consuming, and reduce the attractiveness of ToD applications. These issues can be solved if the performance degradation can be predicted and there is enough time for the remote driver to either park the ToV slowly in the safety lane, reduce speed, or change the route to the destination depending on the predicted Quality of service.

Therefore, tools and frameworks enabling the prediction of such changes can be a game changer for ToD. For that reason, many research work and standard specifications proposed solutions for early notification about QoS changes.

The 3GPP has provided the *QoS sustainability analytics* service in the NWDAF [12], which notify the ToD application about predicted QoS change. As show in Figure 13, the V2X Application Function (AF) can subscribe to the service through the Network Exposure Function (NEF) indicating list of analytics and their reporting thresholds, time interval, preferred level of accuracy, and the area of interest (optional), etc. The NWDAF collects statistics and data from the Operations, Administration, and Maintenance (OAM), processes them and derives the requested analytics and response related to requested QoS change. Then, these analytics or response are relayed to the AF through the NEF. When the AF receives the response, it can make the necessary decision. This framework has two main drawbacks/challenges in current deployment:

- Most of commercial and test 5G networks still missing the NWDAF.
- The granularity of the results provided by the OAM is 15 minutes and in some cases 1 minute, which can be very long for the case of ToD as it will be discussed later.

Figure 13: Procedure of the NWDAF QoS sustainability analytics service [3GPP23-288].

Following this architecture, two questions are mainly investigated:

- How is the prediction performed?

- What action is performed when the QoS is degraded?

The authors of [BLL+24] [13] [KKP+21] [15] study how QoS prediction can be used in different use cases of V2X communications. In [KDS+21] [16], the authors devise a latency prediction model based on deep learning and passive probing for route selection of autonomous vehicles.

The authors in [KMP+21] [15] extend the 3GPP solution based on historical information. The data are collected from both OAM and Radio Resource Control (RRC) measurements are injected into a ML algorithm that is trained offline. When a QoS degradation is detected, the ToD application is notified, and the uplink quality of videos is reduced.

In [BMK+21] [17], a recurrent neural networks model was proposed to predict QoS degradation for CAM applications. They design Long short-term memory (LSTM) network to identify patterns in network metrics and use it to predict QoS degradation.

In [BLL+24] [13], the authors propose a regression neural networks model in a federated learning fashion for estimating packet-based QoS metrics (latency and packet loss rate) derived from 5G network measurements in the context of V2X communication. The same approach of decentralized predictive QoS for V2X was proposed in [BLV+23] [18] **Error! Reference source not found.** and they use their model to estimate the optimal level of compression to be used.

The authors in [AK22] [19] exploit information about network performance to change the route of the autonomous vehicle. Although it is devised for autonomous vehicles, but similar approach can be used for ToD.

In all above research, the prediction is either performed using time prediction or assuming network performance is known through an Oracle. The approach that we took in TARGET-X is different and consists of extracting network performance information through a customized exposure API and providing the remote driver with warnings about congested/disconnected cells in its path towards its destination. Therefore, the prediction in our case is route-based and not time-based location.

4.2.1 Exposure Interface

The main idea of the predictive QoS function for ToD in TARGET-X is to provide the ToD system with information about network status and performance on the path to be taken by the ToV. In other words, the developed functionality will notify the remote driver of any drop in the performance of the network in the next sections of the road of the ToV. Therefore, we are not considering time prediction in this concept but rather spatial prediction.

Figure 14: Predictive QoS for ToD concept example. A cell with low coverage is ahead of the ToV. The PF in this case will detect the low coverage cell and send a warning to the ToC

As shown in Figure 14, we developed a Prediction Function (PF) that periodically extracts information from the network, assess, and notifies the ToC with warnings about low coverage cells or cells with congestions. The detailed information about the deployment of the PF is provided in Section 6.3.

4.2.2 ToC decision

When the ToC receives a warning, it can take one of the following decisions:

- Slowly and safely park the ToV in the right lane or nearby rest area.
- Send an alarm to drivers inside the ToV, in case the ToD is executed to give the driver (for instance of long-distance truck) some rest.
- Decrease the speed of the ToV in case the warning is about congested area and the QoS is still enough to drive the ToV at lower speed. This can be accompanied by a decrease in the quality of the send videos by the ToV.
- Change the route of the vehicle to avoid the congested/low coverage area.

5 Measurements tools and network performance

This section summarizes the results of 5G-NSA network performance testing conducted at the IDIADA test track as part of the WP4 TARGET-X project. The purpose of this assessment was to evaluate the network performance under various conditions including stationery and mobility scenarios. The following sections cover the tools used for data collection and analysis, network coverage findings, performance benchmarks, and latency measurements.

5.1 Qualcomm devices

The following devices were used in the test campaign.

- **Test Devices:** Qualcomm MTP (Mobile Test Platform) devices were used to collect detailed network measurements.
- **PCTel Radio Frequency (RF) Scanner:** A PCTel scanner capable of monitoring cellular technologies from 2G to 5G, covering both low Sub-6 and high mmW bands, was employed to collect radio frequency data.
- **Logging Software:** QXDM was used for the test devices, while SeeHawk software was utilized for processing scanner data.

Figure 15: Qualcomm Tools.

These tools enabled the collection of a broad spectrum of network metrics, including coverage, signal quality, throughput, and latency, across multiple frequency bands (N78, B1, and B3).

5.2 Performance results

5.2.1 Coverage

RF scanner measurements are shown on the next 6 figures, each illustrating the coverage and best server (strongest cell) maps for the N78 (Figure 16), B1 (Figure 17, 18), and B3 (Figure 19, 20) bands. The Cumulative Distribution Functions (CDFs) were also included to provide a detailed statistical breakdown of the coverage. The results show strong coverage across the entire test area, including the IDIADA buildings, Highspeed Lap, and TOV UC Lap (predictive QoS for ToD Use Case Lap).

The Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) 95%-tile for each band are:

- -96.18 dBm for N78
- -97.08 dBm for B1
- -93.09 dBm for B3

As it can be seen in the figures, no significant coverage holes were observed, indicating that the network is well-equipped to provide reliable service throughout the test areas.

Figure 16: 5G n78 band RSRP.

B1 Best Server | Scanner Measurements

Confidential – Qualcomm Technologies, Inc. and/or its affiliated companies – May Contain Trade Secrets 18

Figure 17: 4G B1 band Best server

B1 RSRP | Scanner Measurements

Figure 18: 4G B1 band RSRP.

B3 Best Server | Scanner Measurements

Figure 19: 4G B3 band Best server.

B3 RSRP | Scanner Measurements

Figure 20: 4G B3 band RSRP

5.2.2 Performance

5.2.2.1 NSA Stationary Near Cell Baseline DL Throughput

This test measured downlink (DL) throughput in a stationary scenario near the serving cell. The peak E-UTRAN NR Dual Connectivity (EN-DC) DL throughput reached 1014 Mbps, with an average of 828 Mbps over a test duration of 294 seconds, as shown in Figure 21. The left side of the figure displays average and maximum achieved L1 throughput, EN-DC as well per component carrier, while the right side shows the test location on the map.

As per the New Radio (NR) Leg Contribution (the portion of total throughput provided by 5G NR component in EN-DC setup), we observed the following:

- Average NR Layer 1 (L1) DL throughput: 724 Mbps
- Maximum NR L1 DL throughput: 824 Mbps

Figure 21: NR DL Performance.

From 2, we can see that the NR Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) is 24.4, using 256QAM with 4 MIMO layers most of the time.

Figure 22: DL NR MCS, Modulation distribution, MIMO layers, and scheduling rate.

The average NR DL PRB allocation is 145.6 PRBs (maximum 158.4 PRBs) with a scheduling rate of 91.8%, as shown in Figure 23.

Figure 23 DL RB and PRB.

The LTE leg contributed an average of 126 Mbps, with peaks reaching up to 200 Mbps. These results demonstrate strong network performance with a combined ENDC throughput peaking at 1024 Mbps and an average of 828 Mbps.

5.2.2.2 NSA Stationary Near Cell Baseline UL Throughput

In the uplink (UL) scenario, the peak ENDC UL throughput reached 90 Mbps, with an average of 81.6 Mbps over 260 seconds, as shown in Figure 24. The left side of the figure displays average and maximum achieved L1 throughput, EN-DC as well per component carrier, while the right side shows the test location on the map.

The NR Leg Contribution (the portion of total throughput provided by 5G NR component in EN-DC setup) has the following characteristics:

- Average NR L1 UL throughput: 44 Mbps
- Maximum NR L1 UL throughput: 48 Mbps

Figure 24: NR UL Performance.

The test device was assigned UL NR MCS 27 (64QAM) over 90% of the time, with a single MIMO layer, as shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25: NR Modulation.

The average UL PRB allocation: is 137.4 PRBs (maximum 147.5 PRBs), as shown in Figure 26, with a scheduling rate of 93.7%, as shown in Figure 27 (right side).

Figure 26: UL Average NR MCS

Figure 27: UL RB and PRB

The LTE leg added an average of 38 Mbps (up to 43 Mbps) on top of the NR throughput. These results highlight robust uplink performance under stationary conditions.

5.2.2.3 Highspeed Lap DL/UL Throughput

Throughput measurements were also collected during the Highspeed Lap. The DL throughput shown in Figure 28 showed strong performance with most collected data points exceeding 200 Mbps, and 55% of samples above 500 Mbps. A smaller portion (12.5%) of the route recorded throughput above 800 Mbps.

There were 3% of samples below 5 Mbps, attributed to application layer issues. These anomalies were marked in red on the map and are deemed insignificant for overall performance.

Figure 28: DL Throughput.

The UL throughput shown in Figure 29 was similarly strong, with 69.5% of samples above 100 Mbps and 16.7% of samples exceeding 150 Mbps. Application layer issues caused 4.5% of UL samples to fall below 1 Mbps, also marked in red.

Figure 29: UL Throughput

5.2.2.4 Highspeed Lap RSRP Maps

The RSRP were generated for each frequency band (n78, B1, B3). Orange and red areas indicate where RSRP fell below -100 dBm, highlighting weaker signal areas, indicated in Figures 30, 31 and 32.

Figure 30: NR n78 band RSRP avg

Figure 31: LTE B1 Band RSRP avg

Figure 32: LTE B3 Band RSRP avg

5.2.2.5 Highspeed Lap Best Serving PCI Maps

The maps shown in Figure 33, 34, 35 display the best serving Physical Cell Identity (PCI) for each frequency band, allowing visualization of the cells that served different parts of the Highspeed Lap. The maps also include PDF charts for deeper analysis.

Figure 33: NR n78 band PCI distribution

Figure 34: LTE B1 band PCI distribution

Figure 35: LTE B3 band PCI distribution

5.2.2.6 ToD UC Lap DL/UL Throughput

On the ToD UC Lap, DL performance was exceptional, as shown in Figure 36, with nearly all data points above 200 Mbps, 82.2% of samples exceeding 500 Mbps, and 800 Mbps throughput achieved across most of the route. Only 2.1% of samples fell below 1 Mbps due to application layer issues.

Figure 36: DL Throughput at Urban Area test track.

The UL throughput shown in Figure 37 was similarly impressive, with 98.6% of samples above 50 Mbps and 49.6% exceeding 100 Mbps. Application layer issues led to 1.4% of samples falling below 1 Mbps. This is an important result as this lap will be used for testing and evaluating UC3.

Figure 37: UL Throughput at Urban Area test track

5.2.2.7 ToD UC Lap RSRP Maps

The RSRP maps shown in Figure 38, 39, 40 were generated for each frequency band (n78, B1, B3). Orange and red areas indicate where RSRP fell below -100 dBm, highlighting weaker signal areas.

Figure 38: NR n78 RSRP at Urban Area test track

Figure 39: LTE B1 band RSRP at Urban Area test track

Figure 40: LTE B3 band RSRP at Urban Area test track

5.2.2.8 TOD UC Lap Best Serving PCI Maps

The maps shown in Figure 41, 42, 43 display the best serving Physical Cell Identity (PCI) for each frequency band, allowing visualization of the cells that served different parts of the TOV UC Lap (Urban Area test track). The maps also include PDF charts for deeper analysis.

Figure 41: NR PCI distribution at Urban Area test track

Figure 42: LTE B1 Band distribution at Urban Area test track

Figure 43: LTE B3 Band distribution at Urban Area test track

5.2.3 Latency

5.2.3.1 NSA Stationary Near Cell Baseline Latency

This test measured Round-Trip Time (RTT) to a cloud server under different payload sizes (64 Bytes and 1200 Bytes) and ping intervals (20 ms and 1000 ms). The test location is shown in Figure 44. A CDF chart shown in Figure 45 was used to illustrate the distribution, and a summary table showed minimum, average, median, 95%-tile, and maximum values for each configuration.

64 Byte payload:

- Minimum RTT: 18.8 ms (20 ms interval) and 19.2 ms (1000 ms interval)
- Average RTT: 23.07 ms (20 ms interval) and 22.7 ms (1000 ms interval)

The larger payload showed an approximately 6 ms higher RTT, as expected.

Figure 44: Stationary Latency measurement point

	Min	Avg	Median	95%-tile	Max
cloud_1200b_1000ms	25.20	28.16	27.60	33.30	40.50
cloud_1200b_20ms	25.00	29.54	29.00	35.31	43.10
cloud_64b_1000ms	19.20	22.70	21.90	27.80	114.00
cloud_64b_20ms	18.80	23.07	22.10	29.83	38.90

Figure 45: Stationary Latency measurement results

5.2.3.2 NSA Mobility Highspeed Lap Latency

Latency measurements during the high-speed lap showed similar patterns. ‘High-speed lap’ the is designated name for the route shown in Figure 47 and Figure 48 and does not imply exceptionally high velocities. The actual speed during the tests did not exceed 130 km/h, which is within typical operational ranges and does not impact 4G/5G performance metrics. A CDF chart and tables shown in Figure 46 summarize the RTT distribution. Two maps shown in Figure 47 and Figure 48 were included to visualize the RTT across the route for the 64 Bytes and 1200 Bytes payload cases.

	Min	Avg	Median	95%-tile	Max
cloud_1200b_1000ms	25.20	33.97	29.20	44.67	656.00
cloud_1200b_20ms	25.00	31.13	29.70	38.60	217.00
cloud_64b_1000ms	19.40	25.68	23.20	32.88	298.00
cloud_64b_20ms	18.70	23.56	22.00	29.10	201.00

Figure 46: Highspeed lap Latency measurement results

Figure 47: High-speed lap Latency measurement results 64Bytes

Figure 48: High-speed lap Latency measurement results 1200Bytes

5.3 Measurements conclusions

The 5G-NSA network performance assessment conducted at the IDIADA test track provided a comprehensive evaluation of the network's capabilities across coverage, throughput, and latency in both stationary and mobility scenarios. The results reveal robust overall performance, especially in terms of downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) throughput, as well as stable network coverage across the test area. However, there is room for improvement, particularly in reducing latency for specific use cases.

5.3.1 Coverage

The network demonstrated excellent coverage across all tested areas, including around buildings, the Highspeed lap, and TOV UC lap. No significant coverage holes were detected, with strong RSRP readings across n78, B1, and B3 bands. This ensures consistent connectivity for both stationary and mobile users.

5.3.2 Throughput

The stationary tests near the serving cell showed excellent ENDC downlink performance, peaking at 1014 Mbps, with an average of 828 Mbps. The uplink throughput also delivered strong results, with an average of 81.6 Mbps and peaks reaching 90 Mbps. Mobility tests on the Highspeed lap yielded a similar pattern of excellent DL and UL throughput, with the majority of DL samples above 500 Mbps, and a significant portion even exceeding 800 Mbps. UL throughput also remained strong, with most samples exceeding 100 Mbps.

5.3.3 Latency

The latency tests revealed respectable Round-Trip Time (RTT) metrics, with the stationary scenario showing minimum RTTs around 18.8 ms for small payloads (64 Bytes) and slightly higher for larger payloads (1200 Bytes). While the overall latency is acceptable for most general applications, further reductions are critical for more latency-sensitive applications such, autonomous driving, and industrial automation.

5.3.4 Recommendations for Network Enhancements

5.3.4.1 Deployment of Mobile Edge Compute (MEC)

One key area for improvement is reducing the latency by deploying Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) closer to the network edge, instead of relying solely on cloud-based solutions. MEC can significantly reduce the RTT by processing data locally, near the user, which can be particularly beneficial in scenarios requiring ultra-low latency, such as autonomous vehicle control and immersive augmented/virtual reality applications.

By bringing computing resources closer to the user and reducing the distance that data must travel to reach the cloud, latency can be lowered well below 10 ms in some cases, offering a marked improvement in responsiveness.

As explained in Section 2.1, a MEC has been already deployed in IDIADA network. Performance measurement tests have been conducted and results will be reported in Deliverable D4.3 [20].

5.3.4.2 Optimizing Network Configuration for Low Latency

Additional network optimizations can be made to further reduce latency. These may include fine-tuning scheduling algorithms for more efficient packet processing and transmission, especially in high-demand situations.

5.3.4.3 Localized Network Enhancements

Identifying and addressing specific areas where coverage quality or signal strength dips below -100 dBm (as observed in some areas of the high-speed lap) can also improve both throughput and latency. This can be achieved through targeted deployment of small cells or beamforming enhancements, especially in areas where rapid signal fluctuation is observed.

5.3.5 Conclusion

The 5G-NSA network at the IDIADA test track performs exceptionally well in terms of throughput and coverage, ensuring reliable service for a variety of applications. However, to further optimize the network for emerging, latency-sensitive use cases, the introduction of MEC and targeted network optimizations are recommended. These enhancements will provide a more responsive network capable of supporting the most demanding applications, especially those requiring ultra-low latency.

6 Use cases

In the following section we will describe in depth all information related to the three use cases developed in Task 4.2.

6.1 UC 1 Cooperative Perception

This use case is split in two parts, scenario 1 with a zero visibility intersection between the participant cars, and the scenario 2 where a road stationary vehicle is in the same path of another vehicle in movement.

The background of both scenarios is the same, when a vehicle enters an unfamiliar area, it will receive information from the surrounding infrastructure about the road layout and other static details. This information, combined with data from the vehicle's own sensors and messages from other connected vehicles (like CAM and CPM), allows the vehicle to build a detailed understanding of its environment.

In this use case, all CAVs will generate CPM and CAM messages and send them to the infrastructure, which then forwards this information to nearby vehicles.

The importance of this use case lies in the fact that modern vehicles collect a vast amount of information, both about themselves and their surroundings. By processing and evaluating this data, it becomes possible to anticipate potential events. This means that a vehicle, given the right information at the right time, can enhance its understanding of the situation and adapt its driving strategies, accordingly, ultimately leading to improved safety on the roads.

The main difference between CAMs and CPMs message is the CPMs is created using the perception system of the car (or infrastructure) such as lidars, radars or cameras. For this reason, scenario 1 is not allowed to use CPMs from the cars, as is a zero visibility intersection in where car perception will not detect the other car involved in the use case. For UC1 the messages selected to send information to ITS platform will be CAMs messages.

In UC1, scenario 2, where a road stationary vehicle is in the same lane but with low visibility for a human user, detection from the surroundings will be performed using CPMs messages.

6.1.1 Functional architecture

In this section, the functional architecture diagrams are shown for UC 1: Cooperative perception, in terms of high, mid and low level, and separated between using the same solution deployed in AWS or MEC.

6.1.1.1 High Level

The high level architecture, represented in Figure 49, shows a general overview of the architecture, where CAMs and CPMs message from the CAVRide, and only CAMs from the connected vehicle are sent to the C-ITS platform.

Figure 49: High level architecture

6.1.1.2 Mid-Level

The mid-level architecture adds the detail of the equipment / connections inside each car and the message flow in UL and DL as showed in Figure 50.

Each car has a 5G router that allows connectivity to the C-ITS platform, a GNSS/GPS system with RTK corrections that gives a high precision location and a computer to run the vehicle C-ITS client.

Figure 50: Mid-level architecture

6.1.1.3 Low Level

Low Level adds the differentiation between UL and DL and includes the separation between the deployment of the C-ITS infrastructure over the EDGE (MEC) or over AWS.

Figure 51 shows the UL, and it can be seen all the messages from the car to the infrastructure such as CAMs and CPMs.

Figure 51: Low-level architecture UL - AWS

In DL, showed at Figure 52, the messages sent are the ones from the infrastructure to the cars in order to show awareness of a possible risk. In this case with the infrastructure deployed over AWS.

Figure 52: Low-level architecture DL - AWS

Low level architecture in UL with the infrastructure deployed over the EDGE, this could be seen at Figure 53.

Figure 53: Low-level architecture UL - MEC

Figure 54 shows low level architecture in DL with the infrastructure deployed over the EDGE.

Figure 54: Low-level architecture DL – MEC

6.1.2 Scenario 1

Two vehicles are approaching an intersection with zero visibility (5). These vehicles share their position, speed, and surroundings data with the infrastructure where a Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) platform is deployed over the cloud (AWS) or over the Edge (MEC). The CWS deployed for this scenario monitors all messages from both vehicles and determines if there is a possible risk of an accident by identifying a risky situation. If a risk is identified, it alerts the vehicles so that appropriate actions can be taken. The warning is sent through a DENM, which is displayed on an HMI in both vehicles.

Figure 55: Scenario 1. Intersection with no visibility [TAR23-D41].

6.1.2.1 7.1.2 Dashboards developed

For showing the information to all the users, different dashboards were developed and deployed in the different HMIs. Each car has its own HMI on where drivers could see the information recommended from the infrastructure. In addition, another HMI was developed to show the information from the infrastructure point of view. In the Figure 56 all three dashboards are shown.

Figure 56: Dashboards deployed on the vehicle and infrastructure HMIs.

When a collision risk is detected, the infrastructure, through IDIADA 5G network, spreads the information to all the users involved in the scenario, and a collision warning message is deployed as it can be seen it in the Figure 57.

Figure 57: Dashboards deployed with Collision Risk detected.

6.1.2.2 KPIs

The collected KPIs are the ones defined in D4.1 and are the following: CAM Success RX Rate, CAM Success TX Rate, DENM Success RX Rate and Data transfer Latency.

6.1.3 Scenario 2

Figure 58 shows a roadside damaged vehicle is in the same path of another vehicle in movement. The complexity in this scenario is the lack of visibility due to weather conditions (e.g. heavy rain, fog, or snowfall). Thanks to the CAMs and CPMs messages sent by the vehicles themselves (both from the damaged vehicle and the moving vehicle), the CWS can identify the risk and notify the vehicles using DENM messages of the existence of a damaged vehicle on the same trajectory to avoid a possible accident. The DENM will be displayed by the vehicle through its HMI.

Figure 58: Scenario 2. Damaged vehicle is in the same lane

6.1.3.1 Dashboards developed

In the same way than in Scenario 1, three dashboards show the three different points of view, as showed in Figure 59.

Figure 59: Dashboards deployed

Also, when a collision risk is detected, the system sends warnings to both users This could be seen in Figure 60.

Figure 60: Dashboards deployed with Collision Risk detected

Note: Up to the date, CPMs perception is under development and testing. All test were done using CAMs.

6.1.3.2 KPIs

The collected KPIs are the ones defined in D4.1 and are the following: CAM Success RX Rate, CAM Success RX Rate, DENM Success RX Rate and Data transfer Latency.

6.2 UC2 Digital Twins

The Digital Twin allows to merge the physical and digital worlds by introducing data from the real world into a simulation and the other way around. In particular, the TARGET-X Digital Twin is focused on saving the V2X data exchanged between the ITS station in a certain road segment or scenario, allowing to use such data for simulations including more complex elements (e.g. autonomous vehicles) and/or for testing of vehicle functions in the real world by means of a VIL (Vehicle-In-the-Loop) validation approach.

The UC2 will reproduce a Digital Twin from the Scenario 2 in UC1, in which a digital object (like a vehicle) will be added to the system and showed in the HMI so that the system reacts in the same way as it will do it if a real vehicle should be involved.

6.2.1 Functional view

Figure 61 shows the high-level architecture of the proposed solution to provide replay functionality, where an external stack will provide a database, a “Recorder” and a “Replay” service.

Recorder: Component able to process all incoming C-ITS messages from the ITS Platform (sent by vehicles, RSUs and other road users) and create required metadata to be properly saved in the database for future use. These metadata consist in:

- `asn1MessageType`: the type of C-ITS message (CAM, DENM, CPM, etc)
- `timeStamp`: the reception time
- `expirationTimeStamp`: the time left for the message to expire
- `topic`: the topic in which the message was received by the ITS Platform
- `retained`: indicate whether the message received is retained (valid for a certain period of time, linked with the `expirationTimeStamp`) or not (only valid for the sending time)

Replayer: Component able to reproduce a sequence of saved C-ITS messages from the database through the ITS platform, to be disseminated via the RSU for C-V2X or to the vehicles directly for 5G. This service alters the originally saved messages, which include timestamps and other time-based fields (e.g. expiration times) of the moment of creation/sending, to currently valid messages as if they were created at this specific moment, making them valid for receiving ITS stations listening to them. This way, simulation scenarios and vehicle-in-the-loop (ViL) tests can run making the vehicles under test believe that there are other vehicles and events around, which are completely virtual and belong to the originally saved scenario.

Figure 61: Functional View of Digital Twin platform

Recorder connects to the external MQTT broker from ITS platform in which all ITS messages from Geomessaging will be published by Message extractor. These messages will all be of the type of ITS Message (adaptation-lib), which has the following structure showed in Figure 62.


```
1 private String unigoneJson;  
2 private EventMessageType asn1MessageType;  
3 private Instant timeStamp;  
4 private Instant expirationTimeStamp;  
5 private String topic;  
6 private Boolean retained;
```

Figure 62: Message structure

Where **unigoneJson** is the JSON of the ASN1 message, **asn1MessageType** is the type of its-message (cam_v2, denm_v2, etc), **timeStamp** is the reception time, **expirationTimeStamp** is the time left for the message to expire, **topic** is the topic in which the message was received by message extractor, **retained** indicate whether the message received is retained or not

6.3 UC3 Predictive QoS for Tele-Operated Driving

The objective of use case 3 is two-folds:

- Assess the performance of Tele-Operated Driving (ToD) when using 5G networks
- Demonstrate the importance of accessing network performance information through advanced 5G features, such as network exposure Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to avoid sudden breaking in the case of tele-operated driving.

Without any knowledge about network performance, a Tele-operated Vehicle (ToV) might be stuck on the road if there is a problem in the network at that region, and there might be a need to send a person/tow truck to pick up the ToV. To solve this issue, a ToV can make use of the information provided by the network through the developed exposure interface in TARGET-X. By using the prediction function developed in TARGET-X, the remote driver will be notified with sufficient time ahead so he can take breaking/rerouting decisions efficiently and avoid *sudden stops* that can create inconvenience and potential obstruction on the road.

6.3.1 Functional view

The functional architecture depicted in **Error! Reference source not found.** is designed to fulfil the requirements of this use case. It includes three main layers distributed over three blocks, i.e., mobile network block, the ToV, and the Tele-operation Centre (ToC) that resides at the edge. The three layers are: communication layer (in green), ToD layer (in orange), and intelligence layer (in purple).

Figure 63: Functional architecture of UC3.

Communication layer

The communication layer incorporates the 5G infrastructure, the ToD AS, and the ToD modem:

- The **infrastructure** resides in the mobile network block and enables the seamless communication between the CVs and the AS. It contains the 5G NSA basic network functions such as the gNBs and legacy core elements.
- The **ToD Application Server (AS)** resides in the edge and secures the communication between the V2X protocol stacks in the ToV and the ToC. It also manages the registration and authentication requests.
- The **ToV modem** resides in the ToV and allows the applications inside it to have connectivity through the 5G network provided by the infrastructure.

ToD layer

The ToD layer incorporates the ToD operator application in the ToC and the In-Vehicle ToD interface in the ToV:

- The **ToD operator application** provides remote driving functionalities, such as receiving information and data from the In-Vehicle ToD interface, supporting the environmental perception building process from the ToD operator, performing the driving tasks and transmitting commands to the In-Vehicle ToD interface, among others. It includes the necessary resources (hardware and software components) needed by a ToD operator, including the HMI for remote driving tasks, gear, steering wheel and pedals, a communication unit and a human ToD.
- The **in-vehicle ToD interface** provides all the necessary functionalities and hardware/software components on the ToV to support remote driving tasks. It includes detection of abnormal events and requesting remote support, collecting and sending sensor and camera data to the ToD Operator App, receiving and executing remote driving commands, etc. Thus, it includes all components offered by a ToD technology provider while utilizing the vehicle interfaces from the vehicle OEM for integration.

Intelligence layer

The intelligence layer incorporates the Prediction Function (PF) client in the ToC and the PF in the mobile network:

- The **PF** resides in the mobile network block and contains the required software and APIs required to collect data from network functions, user equipment, and Operations, Administration, and Maintenance (OAM). The collected data is exposed to the PF client in form of warnings when the performance of the network is not as required by the ToD application.
- The **PF** client resides in the ToC and is responsible of interacting with the PF to 1) subscribe to the services provided by the PF, 2) receive warning notification from the PF and process it, 3) and send the recommendation to the Human Machine Interface (HMI).

In theory, the prediction function should subscribe to an exposure API service such as CAMARA's Connectivity insights [CAM24] [21]. However, as the required information to generate the warnings are related to cells in the path of the ToV and the granularity should be in the order of seconds, the current deployment of networks does not enable such deployment. Therefore, we developed a custom PF (See 64).

Figure 64: Custom TARGET-X Prediction Function.

The developed PF was developed using FastAPI framework [22] and it includes the following functions:

- **Master API:** This is the main API that communicates with PF client (or any other application function) on the northbound interface and the transformation function (Cell ID retrieval API and QoS Monitoring API) on the southbound interface. Based on the subscription made by the PF client, the master API decides about the transformation functions to be used and the procedure to be followed. In our case, only cell retrieval and QoS monitoring APIs will be used.
- **Cell ID retrieval:** This API is responsible for retrieving the cell ID of a UE identified by its IP address/IMSI/MSISDN. The IP address is the one used by the PF client to subscribe and it corresponds to the IP of ToV.
- **QoS monitoring API:** This API is responsible for monitoring the QoS in the UE cell or neighbor cells. The cell ID is obtained from the cell ID retrieval API, and the neighbor cells are obtained

from network topology. This API monitors two types of information: cell status and performance KPIs. The former is obtained from a network dashboard that provides information about the status of the cells. This information is updated every 15 minutes as provided by the OAM. The performance KPIs are obtained from an MQTT broker that emulates the nonexistent MWDAF. To emulate the needed information, a connected vehicle will be present on the track and send information about network performance every 1 second. The reported KPIs are:

- Uplink jitter
- Uplink throughput
- Uplink reliability
- Downlink reliability
- Downlink latency
- Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP)
- Signal-to-Interference-Plus-Noise Ratio (SINR)

The PF client developed for this case relays the warning provided by the PF to the HMI. In a more general case, it can provide more intelligent recommendations such as reduce the speed to X kmph, stop the vehicle, change the route following *exist Y*.

6.3.2 KPIs

The collected KPIs were defined in [TAR23-D41] [23] and are the following: Command latency, data transfer latency, command reliability, data transfer reliability, uplink service data-rate, and downlink service data-rate. In addition to these KPIs, we added also the video jitter in the uplink, which is defined as the average difference between successive data transfer latency values.

6.4 KPIs Dashboard Tool

In order to have exhaustive real-time control of the network indicators, a KPI dashboard has been developed in which metrics from the cameras, the commands sent by the remote controls of the remote-controlled car and the network status reported by the 5G routers can be viewed.

All these indicators are plotted in Grafana and KPIs can be viewed in real time or in an historic mode.

Figure 65 shows the data input to Grafana.

Figure 65: Grafana data input

6.4.1 Video KPIs

Figure 66 shows video KPIs defined in D4.1 and showed in Grafana are:

- UL Data Rate
- Video Latency
- Jitter
- Reliability

Figure 66: Video KPIs

6.4.2 Commands KPIs

Figure 67 shows commands KPIs defined in D4.1 and showed in Grafana are:

- DL Data Rate
- Commands Latency
- Reliability

Figure 67: Commands KPIs

6.4.3 Network KPIs

Figure 68 shows network KPIs defined in D4.1 and showed in Grafana are:

- SINR
- RSRP

Figure 68: Network KPIs

6.4.4 KPI Testing Setup

On the following images it can be seen the testing setup with the KPIs screen.

Figure 69: Full testing Setup

Figure 70: KPIs Screen

7 Summary and conclusions

The IDIADA testbed that will be used for TARGET-X automotive use cases' evaluation has a solid and contrasted connectivity infrastructure along all its test facilities that gives flexibility to test with different kind of networks and conditions. Mobile 5G Network used in all the use cases were tested by Qualcomm and there is a recommendation on optimize it to improve average latencies. This has been already done by connecting an MEC server directly to the core network, and service and network KPIs will be shown in the next deliverables.

Perception from the vehicles (CPMs) and awareness messages (CAMs) increase the safety of the roads as one can anticipate manoeuvres to reduce the collision risk in places where the visibility is reduced or directly null. Connectivity should be one more input for the vehicles to increase safety. In the same way, the predictive QoS for Tele-operated driving demonstrates that it will be very important to know the state and the performance of the network where autonomous or controlled vehicles will drive to improve the journey or to reduce sudd behaviours of the vehicles due to a downgrade performance of the mobile network.

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